

e-ISSN: 3048-6017

Volume 09 Issue 01
Jan-Apr 2026

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Submission Date : Feb
11, 2026

Copyright Received
Date:

Feb 12, 2026

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Solid Lubricant based on Spherical Nanoparticles, Their types, Structure Properties & Applications

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ABSTRACT

Science & technology deals with device processing measurement and observation, materials & phenomenon on nanometers scale are collectively known as nanotechnology. The reduction of friction is the primary goal behind the purpose for lubrication. Although there are many ways to reduce friction. The most common method is using fluid or semi fluid. Solid lubrication is a key technique when liquid lubricants are unsatisfactory to the advance requirement and nanotechnology based solid lubricants-which are spherical inorganic nanoparticles (non layered structure) are significantly proved to be better lubricants than the conventional lubricants possessing layered structure, even in extremely harsh conditions. Nanolub is the first commercial nanotechnology based solid lubricant in the world. Spherical inorganic nanoparticles have a unique structure of hollow nested sphere that lubricate by rolling like miniature ball bearing and reduce wear and tear, friction between moving objects (like engine part) enabling longer operation and higher efficiency. Present paper deals with the new commercial Solid Lubrication based on spherical nanoparticles as advanced antifriction material that can be used as dry lubricant, Coating and for impregnating parts to reduce friction and wear. Their types, structure, properties and applications.

Keywords: *Solid lubricants, nanoparticles, Nanolub, nested structure*

INTRODUCTION

Layered compounds such as graphite, molybdenum disulphide (MoS₂), and tungsten disulphide (WS₂) are common solid lubricants. Their layers slide over each other and make the parts over them to slide easily (i.e. reduce friction) the edges of the layer are chemically reactive causing them to slowly decompose, break apart and bind to the metal surface and the relative layer size of layered platelets prevent them from entering the pores of the metal, thus they tend to accumulate on the surface and stick to the surface of the part they are meant to lubricate.[1]

The above factors ultimately diminish their lubricating ability causing the metal part to grind against each other and wear down. Thus, there is a need for smaller more stable nanosolid lubricants. AP nanomaterial nanotechnology-based product like Nanolub is one of the commercial solid lubricants based on spherical inorganic nanoparticles. It has surpassed screening test for space application conducted by space technology division material group of the nuclear research centre in Israel.[2]

The advantages of Nanoparticle based lubricant over existing solid lubricant is due to their unique structure of Nested spheres that lubricate is due to their unique structure of Nested spheres that lubricate by rolling like miniature ball bearing, staying cooler and maintaining their function for longer duration. Their Nanometer scale (only 0.1 micron in diameter) enables them to find their way into small voids resulting in increased coverage even on rough surface, enabling their long operation with higher efficiency in harsh environment like high load. It also reduces galling seizing and fretting of metal surface.[3]

**FEATURES OF
NANOTECHNOLOGY BASED
LUBRICANTS
Nano Size**

Their smaller size enables them to penetrate pores, avoiding surface build up and preparation of impregnated self-lubricating part.

Spherical Shape

Nano particles being spherical shows rolling action reducing friction efficiently more than sliding conventional layered compounds. The spherical shape makes them chemically and physically stable as it extends the operating life of machine due to exposed edges absence.[4]

Nested Structure

Nested structure enables the nano particles to act as self-healing lubricants for maintenance free operation.

Above features of nanoparticles differentiate them in their physical and chemical behavior from those of bulk materials. For example, nanotechnology based extreme pressure and anti wear additives were found to have high chemical and physical stability, even under extreme conditions of pressure. These properties impart longer equipment operation, increased efficiency and reduced frequent maintenance. Smaller, more stable lubricant particles reduce wear to extend the life of the moving parts and alleviate friction to work very well on relatively rough surface. This means that surfaces of mechanical parts do not need to be tooled to a highly smooth or glossed finish. The energy can be saved by reducing noise, heat and vibration due to their longevity, high load capability and high physical and chemical stability.[5]

The environmental benefits of nanoparticles solid lubricants are due to reduction of energy consumption and decreased air pollution. They also provide significant economic benefits due to low cost of maintenance, extended equipment's life, and improved machine performance.

Types of Nanoparticle based Solid Lubricant

It was proposed in 1992 that the propensity of graphite to form fullerenes and nanotubes is not unique and it is not

limited to only one element i.e. carbon. Infection with this property is likely to occur in Nanoparticles of any substance with layered structure.

ORGANIC FULLERENE LIKE MATERIALS

They bear nested structure or ball-like structure which are prepared from graphite and graphene by various methods.

Properties of Organic Fullerene like Materials

The first fullerene discovered was the bucky ball, known as Buckminster fullerene. The discovery of buck ball (C60) which has a nanometer scale hollow spherical structure. Buckminster fullerene or buckyball molecules are roughly spherical cage of 60 carbon atoms arranged in interlocking hexagons and pentagons, like the patches on a soccer ball. It is very tough and can be stemmed against a hard surface without damaging it. Its carbon cage structure remains intact even when 30% of its volume is crushed. It is thermally stable. It exists as a discreet molecule unlike the other two allotropes of carbon (graphite and diamond). Because of the graphite-like bond's durability, fullerenes are not extremely reactive.[6]

Applications

Fullerenes do not have any chemical bonding, but they have weak force of attraction i.e. Vanderwaals force. Similar as that of in the layers of graphite, which give same potential to the buckball like graphite.

Properties of Carbononion

Carbononion is one of the fullerene related materials that have closed spherical shells consist of concentric graphite shells. It can be made in several ways, such as vacuum-annealing soot or diamond nanoparticles or by high-energy electron bombardment of carbon soot in a TEM. Carbononion are composed of SP2 carbon atoms and are believed to result from the microstructure of graphite sheets on molecular scale. Carbononion have low friction co-efficient which can be maintained in vacuum where graphite becomes worthless as a lubricant due to absence of assisting agents like water and oxygen to promote lubricating property. Weak intermolecular forces of Carbon nano-onions ensure advantage to cause extremely less wear.[7]

Applications

Carbononion are recognized as a new form of carbon and included in nanomaterial category. Closed structure of graphene sheets leads to weak interaction with the mating materials because only π electrons exist on the surface, which would link through weak intermolecular bonding, which ensures extremely less wear. Provide carbononion's potentially better material.

Nano Particles are Better Lubricants

Layered materials like graphite, MoS₂, and WS₂ are common solid lubricants. The layers slide over each other to reduce the friction, it should be considered that they act as Lubricant only because of their layered structure. One sheet of graphite or carbon atom is not a lubricant, but two sheets are! Hence nanoparticles due to their spherical structure or edgeless structure can act as better lubricant.

Secondly there is a curious belief that dry lubricated bearings can operate at low friction. In fact engineers avoid oil or grease free bearings like plague, because regardless of the coating used the friction is always ten times worse than an oil lubricated situation and over 100 times worse than a pressure fed hydrodynamic bearing.

INORGANIC FULLERENES AND THEIR PROPERTIES

MoS₂

All nanoparticles composed of layered structure can form fullerene and nanotubes. Nanoclusters of MoS₂ are multiwalled nanoparticles with closed edge which is fullerene-like structure. This phase is produced from the respective oxide in a pure form is quantitatively approaching a kg per day. MoS₂ an inorganic fullerene like material, exhibits superior tribological behavior to all known solid lubricants particularly under high load. It also exhibits excess resistance under shock waves pressure of 20 to 30 Gpa with concurrent temperature of up to 1000°C. No evidence for significant structural degradation or phase change was observed, making it probably strongest cage molecule known today.[8]

Application: MoS₂ powder or platelets under heavy load tend to adhere to metal surface through their reactive prismatic edges and therefore efficiencies solid lubricant is hampered, in contrast to that spherical MoS₂ behave like nanoball they do not lose their tribological benefits until

they are completely oxidized or removed. Their beneficial effects such as solid lubricant additives and self-lubricating coating have been confirmed through a long series of experimental research in various laboratories.

WS₂

For the study of tribological properties of WS₂ in comparison to 2HWS₂ and MoS₂ platelets over a wide range of load and sliding velocity, recently inorganic fullerene like supramolecule of metal dichalcogenide material with nested structure similar to that of carbon fullerene and nanotubes have been synthesized. The size and shape distribution of the nanoparticle was studied by transmission electron microscope (TEM). When compared to normal metal dichalcogenides, the average size of WS₂ nanoparticles seems to have outstanding tribological capabilities with a definite load range (PV150 NM/S). The Oxidation of Inorganic fullerenes and their wear track was less than the solid lubricant made of platelets of same chemical compound.

(WS₂). The nanoparticles remain in their round shape due to weak intermolecular forces of attraction. The increase in pressure results in deformation and destruction of these nanoparticles by destroying their tribological properties.

Applications: WS₂ nanoparticles can be used as a solid lubricant in car, aerospace, home appliances and other numerous industries. The nanospheres of WS₂ disintegrate under high pressure, so WS₂ can act as a layered solid lubricant.

Some Common Applications of Nanoparticles as Solid Lubricant

Typical application of nanoparticles is a sliding or reciprocating motion that is required for lubrication to minimize wear. For example:

- 1 In gear & chain layered lubricants cannot be used.
- 2 Ceramic situations in which lubrication additives that are chemically active have not been discovered for a certain surface.
- 3 High temperature application includes fasteners which can easily be tightened and unscrewed after a long stay at high temperature.
- 4 In vacuum most of the lubricants are non effective due to necessity of assisting agents like water and oxygen, nanoparticle used as solid lubricant prove to be effective.

Besides lubrication fullerenes or nanoparticles are useful in following areas.

- Fullerenes precursor mixture for making synthetic diamonds.
- Fullerenes materials which are soluble and functionalize can be used for electronics, solar cells and fuel cells.
- Fullerenes are also useful to clear water and air (Catalysis Separation).
- Fullerenes also find their use as antioxidants, radical scavengers, and in photodynamic therapy.

CONCLUSION

Organic & Inorganic fullerenes and fullerenes like materials can easily be used as solid lubricants and are called nanoparticles. Their tribological properties ensure their better lubrication capacity in advanced requirements, where normal layered lubricants fail to work. The only drawback is due to their smaller size and spherical structure they can get into human body either by inhalation or transdermal. Hence nanoparticles are safe only when they are used suspended in liquid and stabilized with dispersant. Still, they can be used where liquid lubricants or solid layered lubricants are unsatisfactory to the advanced requirements of modern technology. Thus, nanolubs or nanoparticles are extremely strong and roll

along surfaces to provide excellent lubrication. This is simply because the effects are not important at macro scale but significant at microscale and very important at nanoscale.

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